

Photon Wave Features Contained in Special Relativity?

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A photon is known to satisfy $E=pc$ (from special relativity with $m_0=0$) which is reminiscent of $v=\text{frequency} \times \text{wavelength}$ if $\text{wavelength} = \text{constant}/p$ and $\text{frequency} \times \text{constant}=E$. This, however, may be coincidental.

We consider the Lorentz transformation developed for a rest mass m_0 and define a photon as an object with some E and a p in this rest frame of the particle. We then consider the average of its energy and momentum based on two frames, one moving with constant v and the other with constant $-v$. We first note that unlike a particle with rest mass whose energy transforms to $m_0 c^2 / \sqrt{1-vv/cc}$, the photon has two different energies based on the sign of v , namely $E' = \gamma E(1+v)$ and $E_2' = \gamma E(1-v)$, where $\gamma = 1/\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$. In other words, the energy of the photon distinguishes its direction of motion. This is analogous to the Doppler shift feature of a wave, but this too may be coincidental. Next, one may show that the average photon energy is E_g and the average photon momentum, p_g . In other words, both average quantities mimic the transformation of $m_0 c^2$. Now a trapped photon might be considered to be a rest mass, but it only represents one value, so we argue that γE and γp should be equal (considering $c=1$). This yields $E=pc$ which together with the Doppler shift feature more strongly suggest that the photon behaves as a wave with $\text{constant}/E = \text{frequency}$ and $\text{constant}/p = \text{wavelength}$.

Special Relativistic Features of a Photon

The Lorentz transformation:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \gamma & \gamma v \\ \gamma v & \gamma \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

may be derived strictly for a particle with rest mass such that $x=0$, t in the rest frame transforms to $x'/t'=v$ in a moving one. Considerations of Lorentz invariants leads to:

$$-E^2 + p^2 = m_0^2 c^4 \quad (c=1) \quad (2)$$

(This assumes (x,t) and (p,E) transform according to (1).)

If one sets $m_0=0$, one has $E=pc$. This might be assigned to a photon which cannot be at rest and is reminiscent of:

$C = \text{frequency} \times \text{wavelength} \quad (3)$ for a wave if $\text{frequency constant} = E$ and $\text{wavelength} = \text{constant}/p$. This identification, however, may be coincidental.

We next consider a photon as an object with E and p in the rest frame of m_0 . At this point, no relation between p and E is known. This photon may be observed by two different frames, one moving with v and the other constant $-v$. Then:

v frame: $E' = E \gamma(1+v)$ ((3a)) and -v frame $E_1' = E \gamma(1-v)$ ((3b))

In other words, each frame sees a different energy based on the direction of v. This is reminiscent of frequency in the Doppler shift case which is consistent with $E=pc$ with $E=\text{constant} \cdot f$ and $p=\text{constant}/\text{wavelength}$.

We next note that the average energy of the photon (averaged over the two frames) is:

$$\text{Ave photon energy} = \gamma E \quad ((4))$$

The average momentum (averaged over the two frames) is: γp ((5))

Even if one did not have the inner product relation $-EE+pp = -m_0^2 c^4$, one could consider that a trapped photon would be like a rest mass. In such a case, the trapped energy ($m_0 c^2$) would transform as $m_0 c^2 \gamma$. There can only be one trapped rest energy and so:

$$p=E/c \text{ for } c=1 \text{ or } pc=E \quad ((6))$$

We suggest that the Doppler feature of the photon energy together with $E=pc$ may point in the direction of:

$$E = \text{constant} \cdot \text{frequency} \quad \text{and} \quad p = \text{constant}/\text{wavelength} \quad ((7))$$

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider the Lorentz transformation developed strictly for a particle with rest mass m_0 . We then suggest that a photon is a particle with a p and E in the rest frame of the massive particle, but that there is no relation between p and E . Whereas as $(0, m_0 c^2)$ transforms to $E = m_0 c^2 \gamma / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ and $p = m_0 v \gamma / \sqrt{1-v^2/c^2}$ for both a frame moving with v and $-v$, a photon energy transforms as $E_1 = \gamma E(1+v)$ and $E_2 = \gamma E(1-v)$ ($c=1$). This means that the photon energy shows the direction of motion very much like the frequency in a Doppler shift scenario. If this relation may be carried further one may note that a Doppler wave satisfies: $\text{velocity} = \text{frequency} \cdot \text{wavelength}$. If one considers average p (averaged over the two frames) then it is γp while average energy is γE . If one considers a trapped photon energy to be equivalent to rest mass, then there can only be one rest mass and $\gamma E = \gamma p$ or $E=p$ ($c=1$) or $E=pc$. This is of the form of a classical wave if $E = \text{constant} \cdot \text{frequency}$ and $\text{wavelength} = \text{constant}/p$. This is consistent with the Doppler shift feature of the energy.